

Temporal differentiation and integration based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous multicore fiber

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Abstract—We propose and experimentally demonstrate, for the first time to our knowledge, photonic temporal differentiation and integration on a customized dispersion-diversity 7-core heterogeneous multicore fiber. We successfully demonstrate up to 4th-order temporal differentiation and 7-sample temporal integration.

Keywords—Space-division multiplexing, multicore fibers, true time delay line, signal processing, temporal integration, temporal differentiation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Optical signal processing has proven essential to overcome the bandwidth bottleneck of electronic devices. Photonic temporal differentiators and integrators are fundamental signal operators for applications such as ultrafast communications, optical computing, or microwave photonics, [1]. A photonic temporal differentiator is a device that performs the time differentiation of an input optical signal, whereas a temporal integrator performs the time integral. In this last case, if the number of samples is finite, the integral has a certain time validity. Different implementations have been reported for these basic elements, including fiber grating configurations, [2], and integrated solutions, [3]. Here, we propose and experimentally demonstrate, for the first time to our knowledge, photonic temporal differentiation and integration based on a customized dispersion-diversity heterogeneous multicore fiber (MCF).

II. RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the principle of operation for the proposed time differentiation (1) and time integration (2) systems. It consists of the propagation of a temporal signal along the cores of a dispersion-engineered heterogeneous MCF [4] to obtain time-delayed replicas of the original signal to be properly combined. The MCF has a length of 5 km and comprises 7 different dispersion-engineered cores whose chromatic dispersions are tailored “à la carte” to provide a constant differential group delay between cores tunable with the optical wavelength, [5]. The core group delay dependence with the optical wavelength is shown in the upper inset of Fig. 1. We use an electrical arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) to generate different input waveforms. A filtered broadband source is used as the optical carrier to avoid optical coherence at photodetection. The modulated optical signal is generated by an electro-optic modulator (EOM) and injected into the 7 cores of the MCF. At the fiber output, a set of variable optical attenuators (VOAs) control the sample amplitudes. Then, depending on the functionality, the signal samples are detected differently: in (1) odd-/even-numbered core outputs are connected to the corresponding branch of the balanced photodetector to obtain the positive/negative pulses; and in (2) all core outputs are combined and detected at a single photodetector. A digital phosphor oscilloscope (DPO) measures the temporal signal.

Fig. 1. Operation principle and experimental setup for (1) time differentiation and (2) time integration based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF. BS: Broadband Source; RF: Radiofrequency; EDFA: Erbium doped fiber amplifier; PD: photodetector; BPD: Balanced photodetector.

Fig. 2. Measured (a) first-, (b) second- and (c) forth-order time differentiators at $\lambda = 1560$ nm. (d) Measured first-order temporal differentiator for 3 different optical wavelengths. Measured 7-sample temporal integrators for (e) “10...0”, (f) “1010...0” and (g) “10110...0” sequences at 2 different optical wavelengths.

Fig. 2 shows the experimental results for the proposed architectures. For the time differentiation, we use an 800-ps-width square RF input pulse (see inset of Fig. 2(a)). Fig. 2(a-c) represent, respectively, the measured time differentiator (blue lines) of the first (2 cores), second (3 cores) and forth order (5 cores) at the optical wavelength of 1560 nm. Orange lines depict the numerical differentiator computed from the measured input signal. The experimental results are in a good agreement with the numerical ones, with small discrepancies on the higher-order differentiators mainly caused by the low-power taps required to implement the higher-order differentiators. Fig. 2(d) illustrates the measured 1st-order differentiator for 3 different optical wavelengths. As the optical wavelength increases from 1540 up to 1560 nm, the differential delay between samples increases from 50 up to 150 ps (see the group delay slopes of Fig. 1), so that the overlap between samples decreases and the differentiated signal is broader but less noisy.

For the time integrator, we generate a 64-bit array with an 80-ps bit period. Fig. 2(e-g) show the measured time integrators when the input signals are, respectively, ‘10...0’, ‘1010...0’ and ‘10110...0’. Blue and orange lines represent the measured 7-sample time integrators at the optical wavelengths of 1540 ($\Delta\tau = 50$ ps) and 1546 nm ($\Delta\tau = 80$ ps), respectively, while black-dashed lines depict the computed numerical integrator with 400 samples and $\Delta\tau = 20$ ps. Experimental and numerical results show a good agreement up to a certain temporal duration (the integral validity range) given by $N \cdot \Delta\tau$, being N the number of samples. The largest temporal validity range (560 ps) is achieved when $\Delta\tau$ equals the bit period (at $\lambda = 1546$ nm). We observe some ripples since the input bits have a gaussian shape at both ends. At $\lambda = 1540$ nm, the integral temporal validity decreases down to 350 ps, but the rippling effect is also reduced.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

We have proposed and experimentally demonstrated, for the first time to our knowledge, temporal differentiation and integration based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF. The MCF is 5-km long and comprises 7 different trench-assisted cores whose refractive index profiles were designed to behave as a tuneable sampled TTDL. We successfully demonstrated up to 4th-order time differentiation of an 800-ps-width square signal and 7-sample temporal integration up to a 7-bit sequence with a bit period of 80 ps and an integral validity time of 560 ps. One of the major advantages of our approaches is that they offer remote system reconfigurability, that is, both schemes can be remotely readapted according to the signal to be processed by properly tuning the optical wavelength of operation. For the temporal differentiator, the tunability controls the pulse broadening of the differentiated signal, while for the temporal integrator it can be accommodated to the signal bit rate and it also determines the integral validity time.

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